

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Relationship among Latin American rice breeding sites for disease evaluation

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Latin American countries exchange germplasm through several mechanisms, a major one being the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER)-Latin America. Countries expect certain desirable traits when requesting for germplasm. One important characteristic is disease reaction. To characterize germplasm for distribution, INGER-Latin America uses a disease "hot spot," located at the Santa Rosa Experimental Station (SRES), Villavicencio, Colombia.

More than 80 rice varieties have been released in the region through this mechanism. The efficiency of the exchange system needs to be improved, however, and the relationship among breeding sites needs to be better known. We estimated the level of coincidence among evaluations at SRES and four other breeding sites in Latin America.

We tested 46 commercial varieties and breeding lines in Villavicencio and Palmira, Colombia; Cristina, Guatemala; Goiânia, Brazil; and Juma, Dominican Republic during 1991-92. We evaluated

Table 1. Average disease reaction at 5 locations in Latin America.* 1991-92.

Location	Bl ^b	PB	LSc	Gd
Cristina	1.7**	2.7**	3.1 ns	1.8**
Goiânia	2.6**	4.9**	2.3**	3.3**
Juma	0.0**	2.5**	2.3**	1.4**
Palmira	0.0**	0.0**	0.0**	1.2**
SRES	3.4	3.7	3.4	4.0

*All values were compared with SRES, Villavicencio, using the *t* test. ** = difference significant at 1% probability, ns = difference not significant. ^bEvaluation of disease reaction was based on the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, Bl = leaf blast, PB = panicle blast, LSc = leaf scald, and Gd = grain discoloration.

Table 2. Percentage of coincidence among the susceptible lines at SRES, Villavicencio, and the same lines in 2 other locations.* 1991-92.

Location	Bl	PB	LSc	Gd
Cristina	33 (5)	85 (15)	27 (6)	0 (1)
Goiânia	0 (2)	75 (24)	0 (3)	11 (4)
SRES	100 (12)	100 (13)	100 (11)	100 (19)

*Values in parentheses refer to the number of susceptible lines.

disease reaction for leaf blast (Bl), panicle blast (PB), leaf scald (LSc), and grain discoloration (Gd) using IRRI's 1988 *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Disease reaction was analyzed using the *t* test. Overall averages of each site were compared with that of SRES. To calculate the level of coincidence, we used only materials that were susceptible at SRES (score ≥ 4). If all materials were used, the resistance reaction in a low disease-pressure site would be misleading. Percentage of coincidence was estimated as number of susceptible lines at a given location that coincide with those susceptible at SRES divided by total number of susceptible lines at SRES and the result multiplied by 100.

SRES had the highest average scores for all four diseases, except at Goiânia for PB (Table 1). Highly significant differences existed between SRES and all other sites for all diseases, except at Cristina for LSc. Palmira seemed to be a

location without disease pressure, confirming several reports about disease pressure at SRES.

We estimated the percentage of coincidence among the susceptible lines at SRES and the same lines at Cristina and Goiânia (Table 2). Palmira and Juma were not included because no lines in those places had susceptible reactions. The highest values were obtained for PB at Cristina (85%) and Goiânia (75%), suggesting a high degree of relationship of information on germplasm evaluation among the sites. Latin American countries can use data from the three sites to guide exchanges if PB is of concern. Differences in fungal races and environmental conditions can explain some of these results. The higher coincidence for PB than for Bl suggests that race and/or site by race-specific interactions are more important for Bl than for PB. ■

In vitro propagation of conserved rice germplasm

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Some conserved rice varieties and wild rices are poorly adapted to the locations of genebanks and sometimes produce very few or no seeds. Several wild rice populations are sterile. As a consequence, seed stocks are limited for rejuvenation and distribution, and some conserved accessions are maintained in a vegetative state. In vitro propagation can be used more safely and efficiently than in vivo propagation for increasing plants of these

accessions. Another advantage is that plantlets in sterile media can be safely distributed to requesters worldwide.

We conducted two experiments to determine the best protocol for in vitro propagation of conserved germplasm. The first used seeds to proliferate plantlets of wild *Oryza* species. The second used immature panicles of *O. sativa* to develop calli from which plants were regenerated.

In the first experiment, nine accessions of wild rices representing *O. rhizomatis* (CC genome) and diploid (BB) and tetraploid (BBCC) accessions of *O. punctata* were used for in vitro propagation (see table). Dehulled seeds